

THE MAIN FACTORS AND CRITERIA OF QUALITY EDUCATION

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***Abstract.** The article presents analytical materials on the criteria for assessing the quality education, their components, groups of quality indicators, the role of the qualified teacher in ensuring the quality of education and the criteria for its assessment, as well as the factors that determine the excellence of students.*

***Key words and phrases:** quality education, criteria, qualified teachers, excellence of students, infrastructure, innovation, demand for graduates.*

INTRODUCTION

The quality of the educational process is provided by such factors as educational standards, educational programs, the scientific potential of professors and teachers involved in the educational process, the potential of learners, technical means of the educational process, educational technologies, and the quality level of the management of the educational process. World experience shows that the wide penetration of information and communication technologies and the Internet in the field of education opens a great way for the globalization of educational services. Taking into account such positive aspects in the field of education in developed countries, mass use of information and communication technologies to improve the quality of education is becoming a demand of the time.

RESEARCH METHODS

In the following article, the analysis of scientific and teaching-methodical literature, pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, generalization, pedagogical experiment-test and foresight methods were used.

RESEARCH OUTCOMES AND DISCUSSIONS

Education is an important sphere of public life. Education shapes the intellectual, cultural and spiritual state of society. The content of education and its directions are reflected in educational standards and programs. Considering the quality of education, the following elements must be taken into account:

- owner, disseminator of knowledge;
- knowledge transmitters;
- knowledge transfer technology;
- student;
- level of systematic knowledge;
- necessity and necessity of the acquired knowledge;
- the need and opportunity to obtain new knowledge.

When determining the quality of education, quality indicators can be divided into the following groups:

- quality of teaching staff;
- material and technical base of the educational institution;
- the basis of the teaching staff;
- quality of educational programs;
- quality of students;
- quality of infrastructure;
- quality of knowledge;
- innovative activities of management;
- implementation of innovative processes;
- demand for graduates;

- competitiveness of graduates in the labor market;
- achievements of graduates.

The main focus in the educational process is on the teacher. Therefore, organizing the appropriate education begins with the correct formation of the teaching staff.

The question arises: *how to determine the qualified teacher?*

The teacher not only educates students, he also plays an important role in shaping the personality, worldview and spirituality of future personnel. Therefore, the quality of a teacher is a complex concept, which can mainly include the following:

- level of competence – have high knowledge and experience in a specific field of science and practice;
- ability and enthusiasm to engage in teaching activities;
- observation – quick study of the abilities and characteristics of students;
- ability to communicate with the external and internal environment;
- recognition, position in working field;
- activeness in the field of scientific research;
- existence of a scientific school.

In MOOC (Massive open online course), the teacher's responsibilities change somewhat. Since open education is based on distance learning, there is a certain distance between the teacher and the student. In this case, the teacher is required to coordinate the educational process, give advice, lead educational projects, improve the educational course, and work to improve their qualifications. The educational process in MOOC is based on high technologies, which widely use the achievements of information and telecommunications.

To assess the quality of a professor-teacher, the indicators recommended above are considered unmeasurable factors. In particular, the level of competence can be assessed by a teacher's basic education, academic degree and title, teaching experience and practical experience in a particular field. It should be said here that often when determining the competence of professors, great importance is attached to their specialization in the subjects taught, and this is where the basic information is taken

into account. In our opinion, when determining the competence of a higher school teacher, it is necessary to take into account not only basic information, but also his specialization by academic level and department (or subject) by academic title. Even if one of the three factors correspond to the subject taught by the teacher, his specialty should be considered relevant.

The material and technical base of a higher educational institution is determined by the cost and availability of fixed assets (buildings and structures, machines and devices, laboratories, workstation stock, etc.) necessary for organizing the educational process, conducting scientific research and development.

The scientific potential of professors and teachers of a particular higher education institution is taken into account when justifying the teaching staff. Academic potential is determined as a percentage by the ratio of the number of teachers with academic degrees and titles to the total number of teachers in the main staff. Also, their average age can be taken into account when evaluating teaching staff.

The quality of educational programs is assessed not only by their compliance with the requirements of the state educational standard, but also by the innovativeness of their content.

The quality of students is the most basic and important indicator that influences the final result. Because at the center of the educational process are the consumers of knowledge - students. It is for them that trainings are conducted, educational literature is written, and new educational technologies are developed. For this reason, it is necessary to pay attention to the quality of students when determining the quality education. Because as a result of the educational process, it is they who must provide the latest high-quality intellectual product (personnel).

The quality of students can be assessed by the following indicators:

level of professional knowledge in the field of study (level of knowledge according to AL or KHK);

- level of knowledge of information (computer) technologies;
- knowledge of foreign language;

- enthusiasm, interest in learning in a certain direction (specialty);
- intelligence (intelligence, perception and intellect);
- spirituality;
- talent;
- memory capacity;
- discipline;
- demand;
- opportunity to work;
- observability;
- planning your position.

The quality of infrastructure, that is, the quality of the structure of an educational institution: management structure (number and composition of the rector, vice-rectors, heads of departments, faculties and departments) and the number of administrative and departments. management staff, professors and assistants, optimal and effective management of the educational process, based on the fact that it is sufficient and economically acceptable.

The quality of knowledge is determined by its fundamentality, consistency and how necessary it is in production.

The innovative activity of management and the implementation of innovative processes in an educational institution are directly assessed by the management of the educational process in accordance with the requirements of the time and indicators of management quality.

Indicators of the quality education management are determined by the following principles:

- understand educational management considering scientific and technological development and international educational standards and achieve full compliance with its requirements;
- knowledge of consumer requirements and the ability to analyze strong competition in the labor market;

- regularly improve the educational process based on monitoring results.

When determining the quality of a leader's activity in the education management system, it is advisable to take into account the following characteristics:

- know consumer demand and take it into account when organizing the educational process;
- taking into account the conditions of the educational services market;
- taking into account labor market requirements;
- leadership of the leader ("leadership");
- able to form the composition of the teaching staff and workers;
- process approach to management;
- systematic approach to management;
- able to make informed management decisions;
- ability to use innovative processes in management;
- able to regularly develop the activities of an educational institution.

Factors such as the demand for graduates, their competitiveness and achievements in the labor market are directly related to each other and complement each other. Therefore, the conclusions of managers of manufacturing enterprises are also important in determining the level of knowledge and qualifications of a graduate. To assess the ranking of a university, it is advisable to create and monitor a database on the position of graduates in production.

CONCLUSION

The quality education is determined, first of all, by the quality, level and qualifications of knowledge carriers and disseminators. Knowledge carriers are understood as professors and teachers of a certain higher educational institution and their scientific potential. They teach students using various teaching technologies and methods. For this reason, the modernity of knowledge transfer technology, students' level of proficiency with its help, and the thoroughness and validity of the knowledge gained also play an important role. After a graduate gets a job in production, he also needs to know how necessary the acquired knowledge is. This, in turn, requires the

need to develop the integration of education and production. Scientific and technological progress creates new tools and weapons. In order to introduce modern technologies and technical means into production, organize the production of competitive products suitable for the world market, the graduate is required to constantly study new innovative technologies and techniques in his production work, and there is a need to acquire new knowledge. As a result, in addition to transferring knowledge to the student, it is necessary to form and develop his ability to learn independently. Since most of the above indicators that determine the quality of education do not have quantitative characteristics, based on qualimetry it will be possible to determine the overall result about quality.

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